

Study Protocol

Tablet-based Application for Cognitive Therapy (TACTIC)

Principal Investigator: Prim. Assoc. Prof. Priv.-Doz. Dr. Peter Lackner

Study Staff: Dr. Philipp Schöllauf, Mario Zusag, MSc, Marie-Sophie Müller-Mezin, MSc, Theresa Bloder, PhD, Dr. Burak Bastürk, Dr. Nicholas Calleja-Dincer

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1. Background and Rationale

An important goal of neurological rehabilitation is the treatment of functional deficits in patients following acquired brain injury (ABI). The most common causes of ABI are ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke, spontaneous subarachnoid hemorrhage, and intracranial injury following traumatic brain injury. Depending on its localization, the loss and degeneration of neuronal structures gives rise to a range of functional deficits. Alongside motor impairments, cognitive impairments are especially prominent: Jokinen et al. (2015) found that cognitive disorders are present in 83% of patients after ABI, with half of these patients showing deficits across more than three domains (among them attention, executive function, perception, language, reading and writing, arithmetic, and memory).

The most frequently affected domains are attention (48.5%), language (27%), memory (24.5%), and executive function (18.5%) (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Neurorehabilitation [DGNR], 2022). Because the cognitive processes underlying these domains are interdependent rather than separable, the guidelines recommend a multidisciplinary treatment approach. This recommendation is supported by Kotomi and Ryo (2016) and Marinelli et al. (2017), who showed that speech-language therapy improves outcomes in other cognitive domains, and by Simic et al. (2022) and Fridriksson et al. (2009), who demonstrated the close relationship between working memory, language, and executive function. Optimal treatment of the consequences of brain injury is therefore an individually tailored combination of these therapy domains, delivered by a multidisciplinary therapy team (DGNR, 2022).

Such individualized, multiprofessional therapy is realistic primarily during an inpatient stay. In the DACH region, patients with cognitive impairment after ABI typically receive intensive inpatient neurorehabilitation following acute medical care, but adequate therapy rarely continues once they return to outpatient care. In an analysis of 17,571 adult stroke patients, the Scientific Institute of the AOK (WIdO) reported a median of just 23 minutes of speech-language therapy per patient per week (Korsukewitz & Rucker, 2013), and a survey by the German Stroke Foundation found an average of 76 minutes of occupational or speech-language therapy per week (Stiftung Deutsche Schlaganfall-Hilfe, 2013). Yet the best outcomes are achieved with intensive neurorehabilitation on the order of three to four hours (Breitenstein et al., 2009; Königs et al., 2018). Current standard of care (SOC) therefore represents inadequate provision, under which the majority of patients receive no or too little treatment.

In recent years it has become possible to support cognitive and language rehabilitation with digital technologies that can be used outside the clinic. With this goal, the therapy app myReha was developed through close collaboration between clinically experienced experts in neurology, speech-language therapy, occupational therapy, and neuropsychology and specialists in machine learning and app development. Certified as a Class IIa medical device, myReha allows patients to carry out therapeutic exercises from speech-language therapy, occupational therapy, and neuropsychology on a tablet to improve cognitive deficits. The app draws on a catalog of more than 30,000 tasks, all created by experienced therapists and reflecting the gold-standard exercises used daily in neurorehabilitation clinics. Because it specifically targets the most frequently affected neuropsychological domains (Jokinen et al., 2015), myReha provides comprehensive, guideline-concordant cognitive and language-based neurorehabilitation for patients after ABI.

2. Study Objectives and Endpoints

The aim of this trial is to evaluate whether using the myReha app in addition to SOC improves cognitive outcomes in patients after ABI relative to SOC alone.

2.1 Primary Endpoint

The primary endpoint is cognitive ability as measured by the CERAD+. To express the CERAD+ result as a single scalar value describing the overall cognitive profile, we will apply the validated method of Lillig et al. (2021), in which the z-scores of the individual CERAD+ subtests are averaged without weighting.

2.2 Secondary Endpoints

- Subscores of the CERAD+
- Bielefeld Aphasia Screening – Rehabilitation (BIAS-R)
- Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS)
- Communicative Effectiveness Index (CETI)
- EQ-5D-5L

2.3 Additional Metrics of Interest

- Number of exercises completed
- Cumulative therapy duration

3. Methods

3.1 Study Design

This is a two-arm, randomized, controlled trial in which patients in the intervention group receive a self-adapting therapy regimen supplied via the myReha app in addition to SOC, while patients in the control group receive SOC alone. SOC may include speech-language therapy, occupational therapy, and/or neuropsychology. Study participation spans 12 weeks for both groups. Participants are assessed at two time points at the study center, the Department of Neurology at Klinik Floridsdorf: at baseline (T1) and after completion of the 12-week study phase (T2).

3.2 The Intervention

The myReha app evaluated in this trial is a digital rehabilitation platform operated by patients on a tablet. It covers a variety of therapy-relevant areas of cognitive therapy, specifically attention, arithmetic, executive function, memory, language, and perception; and offers evidence-based exercises in each area at several graded difficulty levels. All exercises were designed in accordance with the neurorehabilitation guidelines of the DGNR and are drawn from routine clinical practice; comparable procedures are documented in standard works of neurorehabilitation, such as those by Schneider et al. (2014) and Habermann and Kolster (2020).

3.3 Study Population

The study population comprises patients with cognitive impairment following a brain injury that occurred more than four weeks earlier. By definition, eligible brain injuries are those captured by the following ICD-10 codes, all of which entail loss and degeneration of neuronal brain tissue with consequent cognitive impairment: S06, I60–I64, and I69.

Sample size

The target sample size is informed by effect sizes for cognitive training reported in the meta-analysis by Gavelin et al. (2020), which identified effects ranging from $d = .13$ to $d = .64$ across 19 studies. Based on the mean effect size of $d = .385$, a two-sided alpha of .05, and power of .80, and assuming a 15% dropout rate, a target of 200 participants (100 per arm, 1:1 allocation) was derived. This sample size was calculated as a deliberately conservative approximation, based on a two-group comparison of the primary summary score (the CERAD+ Total z-score); the planned linear mixed-effects analysis (see Section 4) is expected to be at least as powerful, as it adjusts for baseline performance and uses all available repeated measures rather than a single summary comparison. The derived sample size is therefore considered adequate-to-conservative for the primary analysis. No interim analyses or stopping rules are planned.

Inclusion criteria

- Adults ≥ 18 years with documented ABI occurring >4 weeks prior to study entry
- Impairment (i.e., a z-score ≤ -1.28) in at least one domain (attention, arithmetic, executive function, memory, language, or perception) as assessed by the CERAD+ test battery
- No prior experience with therapy apps for neurological deficits
- Access to a stable internet connection suitable for app operation
- Premorbid German language proficiency at $\geq A2$ level
- Willingness to complete study assessments and regular app use, as judged by the treating clinician

Exclusion criteria

- Inability to operate a tablet independently
- Severe visual or hearing impairment interfering with psychometric testing
- Pre-existing speech, language, or cognitive disorder prior to ABI
- Ongoing or scheduled intensive inpatient/outpatient rehabilitation for the primary condition during the study period
- Severe comorbid illness expected to preclude completion of study procedures

3.4 Recruitment

Patients with cognitive deficits following a brain injury that occurred more than four weeks earlier will be recruited mainly through the neurological three-month outpatient clinic of Klinik Floridsdorf, where they are informed about the opportunity to participate during routine follow-up visits or when these appointments are scheduled; the Department of Neurology at Vienna's St. John's Hospital, and word of mouth. Eligible patients under the care of Klinik Floridsdorf who are not seen in the three-month outpatient clinic may also be informed. Prior care at Klinik Floridsdorf is not required; any patient who learns of the study and meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria may be enrolled through the study center. Enrollment takes place exclusively

at and through the study center of Klinik Floridsdorf, under the direction of Principle Investigator Prim. Assoc. Prof. Priv.-Doz. Dr. Peter Lackner.

3.5 Assessments

The primary endpoint is assessed with the CERAD+ (Schmid et al., 2014), a neuropsychological test developed to evaluate cognitive function in adults. It is a reliable and valid measure of cognitive function in older adults and is widely used in research and clinical settings, comprising tasks that span a broad range of cognitive abilities, including memory, language, visuospatial ability, and executive function.

To capture language-relevant deficits and depressive symptoms in greater detail, the BIAS-R, HADS, CETI, and EQ-5D-5L are included as secondary measures. The BIAS-R, validated by Richter and Hielscher-Fastabend (2006), is a widely used and well-established diagnostic instrument in the DACH-region that is readily administered to neurological patients and supports a qualified assessment of language symptoms across the full range from severe to mild or minimal impairment. The HADS assesses anxiety and depression in patients with physical illness or possibly psychogenic somatic complaints; the instrument and its translations have been extensively validated, and its two-factor structure (one anxiety factor and one depression factor) was confirmed by Bjelland et al. (2002). The CETI is a measure of change in functional communication ability, validated by Lomas et al. (1989) and widely used in studies of communication disorders. The EQ-5D-5L, validated by Golicki et al. (2015), is a widely used instrument for evaluating general effects on health, well-being, and quality of life, all of which can be affected in many ways following brain injury.

3.6 Procedure

At baseline (T1), all participants will undergo neuropsychological screening comprising the primary and secondary outcome measures. After screening, eligible participants will be randomized 1:1 to the intervention or control group using a computer-generated sequence of permuted blocks of size 10, stratified by diagnosis (traumatic brain injury, intracerebral hemorrhage, ischemic stroke).

The intervention group will receive an introduction to the myReha app and a tablet with the application pre-installed, with access to its full functionality for the 12-week intervention period. Participants will be instructed to use the app as often as possible in addition to any SOC services. The app will supply each participant with a new therapy plan daily, adapting continuously and automatically to their needs with the help of artificial intelligence. Use will be self-administered at home and automatically logged for exploratory analyses of adherence. The control group will receive SOC only, without app access. Concurrent SOC service use (e.g., speech-language, occupational therapy, or neuropsychology) will be self-reported and documented to control for potential confounding.

At 12 weeks, all participants will attend a follow-up session (T2) repeating the baseline assessment.

3.7 Blinding

Group allocation will occur at enrollment, after baseline screening, so that assessors remain blinded to allocation during the T1 assessment. Randomization will not be carried out by anyone who will collect outcome parameters, and the central system will reveal only the

individual group assignment at the point of enrollment, with no assessor access to the allocation sequence.

To preserve assessor blinding through follow-up, participant queries during the intervention period will be neither read nor answered by outcome assessors. Before the T2 assessment, participants will be instructed not to discuss their allocation or their experience with the app while outcomes are being collected; because this cannot be entirely guaranteed, outcome assessors will additionally be trained not to ask questions or steer conversations in this direction until the T2 assessment is complete. Given the nature of the intervention, blinding of participants will not be possible.

4. Statistical Analysis Plan

The primary objective is to estimate the effect of the myReha intervention, relative to control, on cognitive-linguistic performance from baseline (T1) to post-intervention (T2). The analysis characterises both the overall cognitive profile and its individual component abilities. The quantity of interest is the difference between the intervention and control groups in change from T1 to T2, with adjustment for baseline performance and for relevant covariates. The between-group difference in change (the group-by-time contrast) is the primary estimate of intervention efficacy.

4.1 Primary Analysis

Longitudinal change will be modeled with a linear mixed-effects model, with the CERAD+ Total z-score (cf. Lillig et al., 2021) as the dependent variable. The model will include fixed effects for Group (myReha vs. control), Time (T1 vs. T2), and their interaction (Group x Time), with Age and Time Since the Neurological Event entered as time-invariant covariates. Concurrent SOC treatment will be included as an additional fixed effect to account for potential confounding. A random intercept is specified for participants to model the repeated measures. The model will use all available longitudinal observations under a missing-at-random assumption and adjust implicitly for baseline performance.

Exploratory subdomain analysis. To explore group differences in domain-specific treatment effects, we will compare CERAD+ subtask performance between the intervention and control group.

All tests will be two-sided with a nominal significance level of $\alpha = .05$. Where multiple comparisons are made within a family of analyses, an appropriate correction will be applied and reported. If any of the assumptions for parametric tests are materially violated, the corresponding non-parametric alternative will be used instead.

4.2 Secondary and Exploratory Analyses

Separate linear mixed-effects models will be fitted for secondary outcome instruments. Each model includes fixed effects of Group, Time, and their interaction (Group x Time), with covariate adjustment (e.g., Age, Time since the Neurological Event, and concurrent SOC therapy provision) and a random intercept for participants.

Exploratory treatment-intensity analysis. As a further exploratory analysis, correlation analysis will be used to examine the association between treatment intensity and the outcome at T2, within the intervention group only, to evaluate whether the amount of engagement with the

myReha App is associated with the extent of a user's cognitive-linguistic gains. Treatment intensity is operationalized as cumulative therapy duration, automatically logged by the myReha platform.

5. Ethics and Dissemination

The trial will be conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The study protocol, participant information and informed consent forms, and all participant-facing materials are reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the City of Vienna (Ethikkommission der Stadt Wien) prior to the enrolment of any participant.

5.1 Consent

Written informed consent will be obtained by a member of the study team authorised by the Principal Investigator before any study-specific procedure is performed. Prospective participants will receive oral and written information about the trial's purpose, procedures, the 12-week duration, the voluntary nature of participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequences for their ongoing care. Participants will be given adequate time and opportunity to ask questions before consenting.

5.2 Confidentiality

Participants are identified in study records by a unique pseudonymous code; the key linking codes to identifying information is stored separately from study data, with access restricted to authorised study personnel. No personal or identifying information will be included in any report or publication.

5.3 Declaration of Interests

The intervention under evaluation, the myReha App, is developed and owned by nyra health GmbH. Members of the study team (Philipp Schöllauf, Theresa Bloder, and Marie-Sophie Müller-Mezin) are employed by or otherwise affiliated with nyra health and have a financial or professional interest in the product. To mitigate potential bias, data are collected by personnel blinded to allocation, and any data analysis performed will be independently reviewed by co-authors who have no affiliation with nyra health GmbH. All authors will have full access to the study data and accept responsibility for its integrity and the accuracy of the analysis. All competing interests will be disclosed in full in any resulting publication.

5.4 Dissemination and Data Sharing

The results of the trial will be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed scientific journal and reported in accordance with the CONSORT guidelines. Summary results will be posted to the trial registry within the required reporting timeframe. The minimal dataset necessary to replicate the findings reported in the primary publication will be deposited in an appropriate de-identified form in a suitable public data repository.

6. References

- Bjelland, I., Dahl, A. A., Haug, T. T., & Neckelmann, D. (2002). The validity of the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale: An updated literature review. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research, 52*(2), 69–77.
- Breitenstein, C., Kramer, K., Meinzer, M., Baumgärtner, A., Flöel, A., & Knecht, S. (2009). Intensives Sprachtraining bei Aphasie. *Der Nervenarzt, 80*, 149–154.
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Neurorehabilitation. (2022). *S3-Leitlinie Neurologische Rehabilitation bei Koma und schwerer Bewusstseinsstörung im Erwachsenenalter*. <https://register.awmf.org/de/leitlinien/detail/080-006>
- Fridriksson, J., Baker, J. M., Whiteside, J., Eoute, D., Jr., Moser, D., Vesselinov, R., & Rorden, C. (2009). Treating visual speech perception to improve speech production in nonfluent aphasia. *Stroke, 40*(3), 853–858.
- Gavelin, H. M., Lampit, A., Hallock, H., Sabatés, J., & Bahar-Fuchs, A. (2020). Cognition-Oriented Treatments for Older Adults: a Systematic Overview of Systematic Reviews. *Neuropsychology review, 30*(2), 167–193.
- Golicki, D., Niewada, M., Buczek, J., & Karlińska, A. (2015). Validity of EQ-5D-5L in stroke. *Quality of Life Research, 24*, 845–850.
- Habermann, C., & Kolster, F. (2020). *Ergotherapie im Arbeitsfeld Neurologie* (3rd ed.). Thieme Verlag.
- Jokinen, H., Melkas, S., Ylikoski, R., Pohjasvaara, T., Kaste, M., Erkinjuntti, T., & Hietanen, M. (2015). Post-stroke cognitive impairment is common even after successful clinical recovery. *European Journal of Neurology, 22*(9), 1288–1294.
- Koršukewitz, C., & Rucker, R. (2013). Relearning to speak properly. *ÄP NeurologiePsychiatrie, 24*–26.
- Kotomi, S., & Ryo, M. (2016). Real-world effectiveness of speech therapy time on cognitive recovery in older patients with acute stroke. *Progress in Rehabilitation Medicine*, Article 102490.
- Königs, M., Beurskens, E. A., & Snoep, L. (2018). Effects of timing and intensity of neurorehabilitation on functional outcome after traumatic brain injury: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, 99*(6), 1149–1159.
- Lillig, R., Ophay, A., Schulz, J. B., Reetz, K., Wojtala, J., Storch, A., Liepelt-Scarfone, I., Becker, S., Berg, D., Balzer-Geldsetzer, M., Kassubek, J., Hilker-Roggendorf, R., Witt, K., Mollenhauer, B., Trenkwalder, C., Roeske, S., Wittchen, H.-U., Riedel, O., Dodel, R., & Kalbe, E. (2021). A new CERAD total score with equally weighted z-scores and additional executive and non-amnesic “CERAD+” tests enhances cognitive diagnosis in patients with Parkinson’s disease: Evidence from the LANDSCAPE study. *Parkinsonism & Related Disorders, 90*, 90–97.
- Lomas, J., Pickard, L., Bester, S., Elbard, H., Finlayson, A., & Zoghaib, C. (1989). The Communicative Effectiveness Index: Development and psychometric evaluation of a

- functional communication measure for adult aphasia. *Journal of Speech and Hearing Disorders*, 54(1), 113–124.
- Marinelli, C. V., Spaccavento, S., Craca, A., Marangolo, P., & Angelelli, P. (2017). Different cognitive profiles of patients with severe aphasia. *Behavioural Neurology*, 2017, Article 3875954.
- Richter, K., & Hielscher-Fastabend, M. (2006). *BIAS A&R: Bielefelder Aphasie Screening Akut und Reha – Zur Diagnostik akuter und postakuter Aphasien*. NAT-Verlag.
- Schmid, N. S., Ehrensperger, M. M., Berres, M., Beck, I. R., & Monsch, A. U. (2014). The extension of the German CERAD neuropsychological assessment battery with tests assessing subcortical, executive and frontal functions improves accuracy in dementia diagnosis. *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders Extra*, 4(2), 322–334.
- Schneider, B., Wehmeyer, M., & Grötzbach, H. (2014). *Aphasie: Wege aus dem Sprachdschungel* (6th ed.). Springer Verlag.
- Simic, T., Laird, L., Brisson, N., Moretti, K., Théoret, J. L., Black, S. E., Eskes, G. A., Leonard, C., & Rochon, E. (2022). Cognitive training to enhance aphasia therapy (Co-TrEAT): A feasibility study. *Frontiers in Rehabilitation Sciences*, 3, Article 815780.
- Stiftung Deutsche Schlaganfall-Hilfe. (2013). *Ambulante Schlaganfallrehabilitation auf dem Prüfstand*. <http://www.perzeptionshaus.de/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/Umfrage-Weiss.pdf>